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Intelligent Electrical Multi Outlets Controlled and Activated by a Data Mining Engine Oriented to Building Electrical Management

Alessandro Massaro, Giacomo Meuli and Angelo Galiano, Dyrecta Lab, Italy

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Forecasting Macroeconomical Indices with Machine Learning : Impartial Analysis of the Relation Between Economic Freedom and Quality of Life

Jonathan Stauer and Patricia Brockmann, Technische Hochschule Nurnberg, Germany

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Design and Implementation of Smart Cooking Based on Amazon Echo

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<http://airconline.com/ijscai/V7N4/7418ijscai03.pdf>